

Indicative questions for fridge/cupboard talks:

- Can you tell me about how you use your fridge/cupboards?
- How do you organise what goes where?
- Do you do this work yourself or do others help?
- What is your favourite item to cook with in your fridge?
- How often do you purchase this item?
- Which items are more challenging to get?
- Is there an item which you are always running out on and find yourself having to replace?

Indicative questions for cook-alongs:

- What are your “staple” or most regular foods and meals?
- What ingredients do you use for this meal?
- How often do you have this meal?
- Where do you find these ingredients?
- What is your favourite ingredient to cook?
- How often do you make this meal?
- Do you like to eat it? /
- What is it that you like about it?
- Do you like to prepare and cook it?
- Can you substitute other ingredients?
- Do you sometimes share this meal for any of your relatives and/or friends?
- Do you ever prepare foods together with your extended family and/or friends?
- How did you learn how to cook this meal?
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Indicative questions for shop-alongs

- Could you tell me where we are going on this shopping journey?
- Do you always take the same journey?
- How often do you go on this journey?
- How often do you shop for food?
- How do you decide what to buy on your regular shops?
- Why do you choose these particular shops or markets or food banks to get your food?
- Why have you bought X, Y and Z?
- Is it difficult to carry some ingredients?
- Are there any ingredients that you find difficult to get?
- Do you find any challenges with your regular food shop?
- How do you usually get there?
- What’s the best thing and the worst thing about your shopping?
- How long have you lived in this neighbourhood?

Indicative questions for map drawing exercises

- Could you draw a line showing the journey from your home to the food shops/markets/food banks that you regularly go to?
- Can you map out a regular and a special meal and the ingredients used on the map?
- Could you mark with a dot on this map of your neighbourhood your favourite food shops/markets?
- Can you map places you might get takeaway or restaurant foods? Could you mark with a dot on this map of your neighbourhood the places that you are important or special for your daily life?